

A Short Review on Alkaloids Occurring in Calabash Curare and Strychnos Barks

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The group of alkaloids which could be isolated from calabash curare and strychnos barks has considerably increased in the last few years. For many of these compounds structural formulas have been proposed. The following tables summarize the available information on the occurrence, empirical formulas, R_e -values, colour reactions, biological activity and (as far as possible) the structure of these alkaloids. The tables contain also the most important references concerning this group of natural products. These tables are an enlargement and a completion of those which had been worked out in the earlier stages of the investigation of these alkaloids^{1,2,46}.

Alkaloids with known structures from Calabash curare and Strychnos barks

(The references pertain to the papers on structure elucidation).

N(b)-Metho-harmin salt
Melinonine F²¹

Melinonine A²⁰

Melinonine B²¹

Melinonine G=
Flavopereirine^{21,30}

O-Mavaourine^{31,32}

O-Fluorocurine^{31,32}

C-Alkaloid Y 13

C-Fluorocurarine 36-39

Lochnerine 29

Lochneram 22

Caracurine VII = Wieland-Gumlich-aldehyde 33,34

N(b)-Metho-Wieland-Gumlich-aldehyde = C-Alkaloid A8 15

Diaboline = N(a)-Acetyl-Wieland-Gumlich-aldehyde 35

R = R' = H: C-Dihydrotoxiferine 40-42,47
 R = H; R' = OH: C-Alkaloid H43
 R = R' = OH: C-Toxiferine 41

(a) R = R' = H: C-Curarine 44
 R = H; R' = OH: C-Alkaloid G43,44
 R = R' = OH: C-Alkaloid E44

(b) } Formula (a) or (b)

Caracurine Va = Nor-C-toxiferine 15,42

Caracurine V41

Alkaloids isolated from Calabash curate and Strychnos barks.

Quaternary alkaloids. Names.	Isolated from Cala- bashes.	Strychnos barks(6).	Empirical formule(6).	Colour reaction with $C_{25}V$ sulphate+conc. H_2SO_4 immediately/after 5-10 sec.	$R_c(6)$ developed with solvent $C(6)$.	$R_n(6)$ in $\mu/kg.$ mice.	Isolation.
C-alkaloid A	+	Mi	$C_{40}H_{48}O_4N_4^{++}$	blue violet/orange	0.23	7	3,4
C-alkaloid B	+	Mi	$C_{40}H_{46}O_2N_4^{++}$	red violet/colorless	0.34	280	3,4
C-alkaloid C	+	Mi, sol	?	red violet/ "	0.34	240	3,4
C-alkaloid D	+	Mi, sol	$C_{40}H_{48}O_2N_4^{++}$	red violet/ "	0.35	1100	3,4
C-alkaloid E	+	tom, sol, Fro	$C_{40}H_{44}O_2N_4^{++}$	blue/light green	0.36	0.3	3,4
C-toxiferine I (= Toxiferine I)	+	tox, tom, Fro	$C_{40}H_{46}O_2N_4^{++}$	red violet/colorless	0.42	9	5
C-alkaloid F	+	sol	$C_{40}H_{48}O_3N_4^{++}$	red violet/orange	0.49	75	3,4
Toxiferine VIII		tox	—	—	0.63		45
C-alkaloid G	+	sol	$C_{40}H_{44}O_2N_4^{++}$	blue/light green	0.65	0.6	3,4
C-alkaloid R	+		$(C_{41}H_{37}O_2N_2)^{+x}$	violet	0.68		6
C-alkaloid H	+	tri, sol	$C_{40}H_{46}ON_4^{++}$	red violet/colorless	0.71	16	3,4
C-alkaloid BL	+		$C_{40}H_{50}O_2N_4^{++}$	blue/blue green	0.75	455	7
C-calcibasine (= Toxiferine II = C-strychnotaxine I)	+	tri, div, sol, Mi, rub	$C_{40}H_{48}O_2N_4^{++}$	blue violet/orange	0.80	240	8,9
C-alkaloid-I	+	tri, Fro, rub	$(C_{30}H_{23-23}N_2)^{+x}$	blue violet/red	0.89	174	3,4
C-curarine-I	+	tri, div, tom, sol, Mi,					
C-alkaloid J	+	su	$C_{40}H_{44}ON_4^{++}$	blue/light green	1.00	30	9,10
C-guainine	+	Fro	?	pale red violet/colorless	1.04	290	3,4
C-dihydrotoxiferine (= C-alkaloid K)	+		$(C_{30}H_{23}ON_2)^{+x}$	blue violet	1.12	35	11
C-alkaloid M	+	Fro, tri	$C_{40}H_{46}N_4^{++}$	red violet/colorless	1.22	30	3,8,12
Alkaloid A8 (= N(6)-metho- Wieland-Gamlich-aldelyde)	+	tox	$(C_{30}H_{23}O_2N_2)^{+x}$	none/yellow (20')	1.45	4.5 mg. inefficient	13,14
C-alkaloid Y (= Profluorcurine)	+		$C_{30}H_{25}O_2N_2^{+}$	orange	1.50		15,45
C-calcibasine	+	sol	$C_{30}H_{27}O_2N_2^{+}$	red violet	1.59		13
Pedamazine	+	tox	?	earmine / light brown	1.68	22000	3,4
C-fluorocurine	+	tox, tom, sol, Mi, mal, sub	$C_{30}H_{25}ON_2^{+}$	blue	1.90	2000	16
	+		$C_{30}H_{23}O_2N_2^{+}$	orange	2.10	4400	17,45

(Contd.)

Quaternary alkaloids. Names.	Isolated from Gala- Strychnos bark(s).	Empirical formulae(φ).	Colour reaction with C ₂₁ v sulphate + conc. H ₂ SO ₄ immediately/after 5-10 sec.	R _c (φ). developed with solvent C(φ).	R _s (φ).	HD(δ) in μ/kg. micc.	Isolation.
C-pseudoefluorurine	+	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ ⁺	red/orange	2.10	—	—	6
C-fluorocurinine	+	?	carmine/wine red	2.23	—	2750	3,4
C-fluorocurarine (=C-curarine III)	+	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ ON ₂ ⁺	pale blue	2.25	—	1800	3,4,18
Toxiferine XII	tox	?	—	2.30	—	—	45
C-alkaloid L	+	?	red	2.50	—	1900	3,4
C-mavacurine	+	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ ON ₂ ⁺	carmine	2.70	—	—	13,19
Melinonine A(=N-metho-py- tetrahydro-alstonine)	mel	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ ⁺	none	—	1.46	—	20,21
Melinonine B	mel	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ON ₂ ⁺	„	2.72	1.00	—	20,21
Melinonine E	mel	C ₂₀ H ₂₃₋₂₅ ON ₂ ⁺	„	—	0.86	—	21
Melinonine F (=Harman- N(b)-methosalt)	mel	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ ⁺	„	—	0.74	—	21
Melinonine G (=flavo- perceirine)	mel	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ ⁺	„	—	1.15	—	21
Melinonine H	mel	C ₂₀ H ₂₁₋₂₃ ON ₂ ⁺	„	—	0.54	—	21
Melinonine I	mel	?	yellow brown	—	0.74	—	21
Melinonine K	mel	?	„	—	0.56	—	21
Melinonine L	mel	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂	pale blue	—	—	—	21
Melinonine M	mel	?	none	—	—	—	21
Macusine-B	tox	C ₃₀ H ₂₃₋₂₇ ON ₂ ⁺	pale grey	3.00	—	—	45
Lochneram	+	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂ ⁺	none/yellow (after 20')	3.10	—	—	22
Macusine-A	tox	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂ ⁺	pale grey	3.60	—	—	45
C-alkaloid O	+	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ ON ₂ ⁺ ?	none (in 50% H ₂ SO ₄ +Cev sulphate: blue green)	3.95	—	7000	11
C-alkaloid P	+	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ ON ₂ ⁺ ?	blue	—	—	2500	11
C-alkaloid X	+	?	orange/red (1-2b)	—	—	—	17
C-xanthocurine	+	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ON ₂ ⁺	blue green	—	—	620	11

Quaternary alkaloids. Names.	Isolated from Cala- Strychnos bashes, barks(α).	Empirical formulæ(β).	Colour reaction with Cev sulphate + conc. H ₂ SO ₄ immediately/after 5-10 sec.	R _D (δ) developed with solvent C(ε).	R _B (δ). HD(ζ) in μ/kg. mice.	Isolation.
Toxiferine II (= Strychno- toxine II(α))	+	?		—	—	8
Toxiferine I(β)	+	?		—	—	5, 23
C-isodihydrotoxiferine	+	?		—	—	8
C-curarine II (= Strychno- toxine Ia)	+	?		—	—	18
Alkaloid 1	+	?		—	—	19
Alkaloid 2	+	?		—	—	19
l-Curine	+	?		—	—	18
Alkaloid γ		?		—	—	24
Macrophylline A	am	?		—	—	25
Opisacurarine III	ma	?		—	—	25
Tertiary alkaloids	gu	?		—	—	26
nor-Dihydrotoxiferine	tox		violet/orange			16, 27
Caracurine I	tox	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₄ ?	purple/brownish	0.7	2000	16, 27
Caracurine II	tox	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ O ₂ N ₄	purple/brownish	0.8	> 16,000	16, 27
Caracurine III	tox	?	purple/brownish	0.8	> 15,000	16, 27
Caracurine IV	tox	?	violet/orange brown	1.0	930(ξ)	16, 27
Caracurine V	tox	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ O ₂ N ₄	purple/brown	1.4	700(ξ)	16, 27
Caracurine VI (= non-C- alkaloid H)	tox	?	purple/brown	1.6	—	16, 27
Caracurine VII (= Wicland- Gumlich-aldéhyde)	tox	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂	orange	2.1	1140(ξ)	16, 27
Caracurine VIII(θ)	tox	?	purple/brown	1.4	1020(ξ)	16, 27
Caracurine IX(θ)	tox	?	red violet/violet brown	1.1	1050(ξ)	16, 27
Ejiboline (= N(α)-acetyl- Wicland-Gumlich-aldéhyde)	dia	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂	none	—	—	28
Lepthnerine (C-alkaloid T)	+	Lepthnera rosea (L.) C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂	light pink	—	—	29
C-alkaloid Q	+	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂ ?	none	4.92(η)	—	6
C-alkaloid S	+	C ₁₉ - ₂₀ H ₂₂₋₂₄ N ₂ ?	red violet	0.51(μ)	—	6

(Contd.)

Glossary:

(a) Mi	=	Str. Mitscherlichii	div	=	Str. divaricans Ducke
sol	=	Str. solimoesana Kruk.	rub	=	Str. rubiginosa DC.
tom	=	Str. tomentosa (Benth.)	gu	=	Str. guianensis (Aubl.) Mart.
Fro	=	Str. Froesii Ducke	mel	=	Str. melinoniana Baill.
tox	=	Str. toxifera Rob. Schomb.	am	=	Str. amazonica Kruk.
tri	=	Str. trinervis (Aubl.) Mart.	sub	=	Str. subcordata Spruce.

Abbreviations indicated by italics signify that the alkaloid has been isolated, in the other case the alkaloid was only demonstrated by paper chromatography.

- (b) Doubtful formulas are designated with ?
- (c) R_c = migrational distance of the alkaloid chloride relative to the migrational distance of C-curarine-I-dichloride.
- (d) R_a = migrational distance of the alkaloid chloride relative to the migrational distance of melinonine-B-chloride.
- (e) Solvent "C" = methylethylketone saturated with water containing 1-5 vol. % methanol.
Solvent "D" = ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (7.5:2.3:1.65).
- (f) "Head-drop" -dosis in μ /kg. mice.
- (g) Perhaps identical with C-alkaloid A.
- (h) Perhaps identical with C-toxiferine I.
- (i) Isolated as chloromethylate.
- (k) HD-dosis of the respective chloromethylates.
- (l) R_c -value with solvent "D".
- (m) R_c -value with solvent "D" = 1.35.

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